

ICT Availability, Usage, and Challenges in Teaching and Learning in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Sapele L.G.A.

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Abstract

This study examines the Availability, Utilization, and Challenges of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in teaching and Learning Processes in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Sapele L.G.A, Delta State, Nigeria. A sample of 150 respondents, consisting of 100 teachers and 50 students, was selected from five randomly chosen public senior secondary schools. The instrument's reliability, determined through Cronbach's alpha, yielded a score of 0.78, indicating reliability. Data analysis employed Excel spreadsheet, with statistical tools includes percentage, mean, standard deviation, Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC), and regression analysis. Questionnaires were used to gather demographic information on age, gender, teaching experience, and academic status. Findings revealed a predominantly young respondent population (71.26% under 25 years), with a higher female representation (61.42%). Most respondents have 1-4 years of teaching experience (60.27%), and 71.26% identify as students, while 28.74% are teachers. The study underscores the importance of enhancing ICT infrastructure and integration to improve teaching, learning, and academic performance in public senior secondary schools. The research findings revealed low availability and limited access to ICT facilities in public senior secondary schools in Sapele L.G.A, Delta State, Nigeria. Integration of ICT into teaching showed a moderate level, with significant challenges hindering effective utilization. However, a strong positive relationship between ICT utilization and academic performance was identified, emphasizing the need for enhanced infrastructure and integration to improve teaching and learning outcomes. The study recommends that the Delta State Government, policymakers, and non-governmental organizations allocate funds for ICT infrastructure and teacher training, develop tailored guidelines, conduct regular assessments, and provide support for ICT literacy in Sapele L.G.A of Delta State.

Key words: ICT utilization, Teaching and Learning, ICT infrastructure

Introduction

In recent years, the integration of information and communication technology (ICT) into the global education sector has gained considerable attention. However, the level of access to and effective use of ICT facilities in the teaching and learning processes of senior secondary school students in Sapele Local Government Area, Delta State, Nigeria, remains a pressing issue. This study examines the challenges and obstacles that limit the efficient use of ICT in education within this region. The research focuses on public senior secondary school students and teachers who utilize ICT facilities in Sapele Local Government Area for academic purposes.

In today's knowledge-driven world, the integration of ICT into the teaching and learning process is no longer a luxury but a necessity for equipping students with the skills required to thrive in the 21st century. ICT tools—ranging from computers, projectors, and internet connectivity to educational software and digital resources have the potential to enhance instructional delivery, promote interactive and student-centered learning, and bridge educational gaps. By providing access to vast information and learning opportunities, ICT empowers

both teachers and learners to engage more effectively with the curriculum, fostering creativity, critical thinking, and collaboration. (Ertmer, 2019; Voogt et al., 2017)

The role of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in education is widely acknowledged for its ability to improve instructional methods and enhance student learning experiences. This section explores recent research on the accessibility of ICT tools, their integration into classroom teaching, and the challenges that impede their effective utilization.

The presence of ICT facilities, including computers, projectors, internet access, and educational software, is fundamental to integrating technology into education. Studies reveal that although some schools, particularly in urban areas, have access to ICT tools, disparities in distribution remain a major issue (Olaleye & Oyewusi, 2021). In Nigeria, inadequate infrastructure and insufficient government investment have been cited as significant factors limiting ICT availability in public schools (Adebayo et al., 2022). Nonetheless, recent initiatives by public and private sectors aim to address this shortfall by supplying digital learning resources (Eze & Nwosu, 2023). While existing literature provides insights into ICT accessibility in Nigerian schools, there is limited empirical data specific to Sapele Local Government Area (L.G.A.). This study seeks to fill this gap by evaluating the extent to which ICT resources are available in public senior secondary schools within this locality.

Despite increased ICT deployment in schools, its actual application in teaching and learning remains inconsistent. Research highlights that factors such as teacher training, attitudes toward technology, and instructional methods significantly influence ICT adoption (Bello et al., 2021). Studies further suggest that when appropriately utilized, ICT fosters student engagement, facilitates differentiated instruction, and improves academic outcomes (Ajayi, 2022). However, a lack of digital literacy among educators and limited ICT-based pedagogical strategies often restrict its effectiveness (Okonkwo & Chukwu, 2023).: Although prior studies discuss ICT usage trends in schools, there is insufficient research on how teachers and students in Sapele L.G.A. engage with digital technologies in their learning environment. This study aims to bridge this knowledge gap by assessing the extent of ICT adoption in public secondary schools within the region.

Several barriers hinder the effective implementation of ICT in teaching and learning. Common challenges include inadequate infrastructure, erratic power supply, high internet costs, and resistance to technology adoption among educators (Umeh et al., 2022). In Nigeria, financial constraints often impede school administrators from maintaining ICT facilities, further limiting their effectiveness in classrooms (Nwafor & Okeke, 2023). Additionally, cultural perceptions and reluctance to embrace new technology contribute to the slow pace of ICT integration (Ogunleye, 2023). While research has explored ICT challenges in Nigeria, there is little focus on the specific difficulties faced by teachers and students in Sapele L.G.A.. This study will investigate these obstacles in detail and propose solutions tailored to the region's unique context.

By examining ICT availability, usage, and associated challenges in public senior secondary schools in Sapele L.G.A., this research fills a crucial gap in existing literature. The findings will provide valuable insights for policymakers, educators, and stakeholders to enhance ICT infrastructure, improve teacher training programs, and develop policies that support ICT adoption in secondary education.

Objectives of the study

The objectives of this study include:

1. To determine the availability of (ICT) facilities in Public senior secondary school students in Sapele Local Government Area.
2. To determine the degree of access to information and communication technology (ICT) facilities among some senior secondary school students in Sapele Local Government Area.
3. To evaluate the extent to which ICT facilities are integrated into the teaching and learning process in senior secondary schools in the area.

4. To identify the challenges and barriers that hinder effective utilization of ICT facilities in education within Sapele local government area.
5. To examine the impact of ICT utilization on the academic performance of senior secondary school students in Sapele Local Government Area.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study

1. What is the degree of availability of ICT facilities in the Public senior secondary schools in Sapele Local Government Area?
2. What is the current level of access to information and communication technology (ICT) facilities among Public senior secondary school students in Sapele Local Government Area?
3. How are ICT facilities integrated into the teaching and learning process in Public Senior Secondary Schools within Sapele Local Government Area?
4. What challenges and barriers exists that hinder the effective utilization of ICT facilities in education within Sapele Local Government Area?
5. How does the utilization of ICT impact the academic performance of Public Senior Secondary School students in Sapele Local Government Area?

Research Hypothesis

1. The utilization of ICT in public secondary in Sapele L.G.A is significantly limited, hindering its effective utilization in the teaching and learning process.
2. There is no significant difference in the current level of access to information and communication technology (ICT) facilities among senior secondary school students in Sapele Local Government Area.

Methodology

This study employed a descriptive survey research design to assess the extent of ICT integration in teaching and learning, as well as its challenges and impact on the academic performance of public senior secondary schools in Sapele Local Government Area (LGA) of Delta State. The study population comprised 681 public senior secondary school teachers in Sapele LGA. A random sampling technique was used to select five out of the fifteen public senior secondary schools for the study.

The ICT Facility Assessment Questionnaire (ICTFAQ), a self-structured tool, consisted of two sections: Section A addressed respondents' demographic details, while Section B featured 19 items on a 4-point Likert scale, evaluating ICT availability, barriers to utilization, teachers' use of ICT in teaching, and access frequency to ICT facilities.

To determine the reliability of the instrument, a trial test was conducted with thirty SS 3 students outside the area under study. In two time the same instruments were repeated on the same group of students. The data gathered were analyzed using Cronbach alpha instrument. A reliability of 0.78 was obtained. Thus the instrument was adjudged reliable.

Data for the study were collected using questionnaires administered to school teachers and students by the researcher and trained assistants to gather feedback on ICT access, integration in teaching and learning, challenges, and its impact on students' academic performance.

The data were analyzed using Excel, with percentages for demographic analysis, mean and standard deviation for research questions 1–4, PPMC for research question 5, and regression analysis to test the hypothesis at a 0.05 significance level.

Table 2 Demographic information on Teachers

Background	Category	Frequency	Percentage %
Age	Under 25	181	71.26
	26-35	34	13.39
	36-45	25	9.84
	46-55	14	5.51
	55+	4	1.57
			254
Gender	Male	98	38.58
	Female	156	61.42
		254	100.00
Teaching Experience	Less than 1 year	5	6.85
	1-4 years	44	60.27
	5-10 years	13	17.81
	11-20 years	8	10.96
	21 years	3	4.11
		73	100.00
Academic status	Teacher	100	28.74
	Students	50	71.26
	Total	150	100.00

Description of respondents on independent variable

Table 2 presents data related to the demographics and characteristics of respondents, focusing on age, gender, teaching experience, and academic status in the context of the availability, utilization, and challenges of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in teaching and learning processes in public senior secondary schools in Sapele L.G.A, Delta State, Nigeria. The majority of the respondents (71.26%) are under the age of 25, indicating a relatively young population in the study. A small percentage falls in the 26-35 age groups (13.39%), with decreasing percentages in the older age categories. Females constitute a higher percentage (61.42%) of the respondents compared to males (38.58%). The majority of the respondents have teaching experience of 1-4 years (60.27%).

Analysis of research Questions

Research Question One: What is the degree of availability of ICT facilities in the Public senior secondary schools in Sapele Local Government Area?

Table 3 Mean and standard deviation analysis to determine the degree of availability of ICT facilities in the Public senior secondary schools in Sapele Local Government Area

S/No1	Statement (n=150; critical Mean = 2.50)	Mean	St.D	Remark
1	The school has ICT facility for academic purposes?	1.83	0.458	Low

2	The ICT facility is equipped with functional computer in your school?	2.08	0.520	Low
3	The school has a reliable internet connection available for teachers and students use?	1.41	0.352	Low
4	There are projectors and or smart boards available in your classrooms?	2.52	0.631	Low
5	There are sufficient ICT resources for all students in your school?	1.67	0.417	Low
6	The ICT facilities is properly managed to ensure they are functional for student use?	1.51	0.378	Low
	Aggregate	1.84	0.459	Low

The table 3 presents a mean and standard deviation analysis to determine the degree of availability of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) facilities in public senior secondary schools in Sapele Local Government Area. The results indicate a generally low level of availability of ICT facilities across various parameters.

The mean score for the existence of ICT facilities for academic purposes is 1.83 (SD = ±0.458), suggesting a limited presence of such facilities in the schools. Additionally, the mean score for the availability of functional computers in the ICT facility is 2.08 (SD = ±0.520), indicating that while computers are present, their functionality may be lacking.

A low mean score of 1.41 (SD = ±0.352) is reported for the availability of reliable internet connections, highlighting a significant deficiency in this essential resource for both teachers and students. The presence of projectors or smart boards in classrooms receives a mean score of 2.52 (SD = ±0.631), suggesting that while available, these resources may not be universally accessible.

Furthermore, the mean score for the availability of sufficient ICT resources for all students is 1.67 (SD = ±0.417), indicating inadequacy in meeting the technological needs of the student population. Lastly, the mean score for the proper management of ICT facilities to ensure functionality for student use is 1.51 (SD = ±0.378), suggesting shortcomings in maintenance and oversight.

The aggregate mean score of 1.84 (SD = ±0.459) reinforces the overall low degree of availability of ICT facilities in public senior secondary schools in Sapele Local Government Area. These findings underscore the urgent need for significant improvements in ICT infrastructure to support effective teaching and learning processes.

Research question 2: What is the current level of access to information and communication technology (ICT) facilities Public senior secondary school students in Sapele Local Government Area?

Table 4 Mean and Standard deviation analysis to establish the current level of access to information and communication technology (ICT) facilities Public senior secondary school students in Sapele Local Government Area

S/No1	Statement (n=150; critical Mean = 2.50)	Mean	St.D	Remark
7	How frequently do you use computers for your schoolwork?	1.78	0.445	Low
8	How often are you allowed access to the school ICT facility for academic work?	1.94	0.486	Low
9	How often to do you have access to a personal computer or laptop at home?	2.73	0.683	Low
10	How often do you use the internet for academic research or assignments?	2.77	0.692	Low
	Aggregate	2.31	0.577	Low

Table 4 above presents a mean and standard deviation analysis to assess the current level of access to Information and Communication Technology (ICT) facilities for public senior secondary school students in Sapele Local Government Area. The results indicate an overall low level of access to ICT resources among students.

Students report low computer usage for schoolwork (Mean = 1.78, SD = ±0.445) and limited access to school ICT facilities (Mean = 1.94, SD = ±0.486). Personal computer availability at home is also low (Mean = 2.73, SD = ±0.683), while internet use for academic research is limited (Mean = 2.77, SD = ±0.692).

The aggregate mean score of 2.31 (SD = ±0.577) underscores the generally low level of access to ICT facilities among students in Sapele Local Government Area. These findings emphasize the need for increased investment in ICT infrastructure in the schools to enhance their access to technology for educational purposes.

Research question 3: How are ICT technology facilities integrated into the teaching and learning process in Public senior secondary schools in Sapele Local Government Area?

Table 5 Mean and Standard Deviation analysis to determine how are ICT technology facilities integrated into the teaching and learning process in Public senior secondary schools within Sapele Local Government Area

S/No1	Statement (n=150; critical Mean = 2.50)	Mean	St.D	Remark
11	To what extent do your teachers incorporate ICT in their teaching methods?	1.78	0.445	Low
12	Do you receive training on how to use ICT tools for learning?	2.46	0.615	Low
13	How effective do you believe the integration of ICT is in enhancing your comprehension of ICT is in enhancing your comprehension of the subject being taught ?	2.33	0.583	Low
14	To what extent can you rate your teachers skills in the use of ICT in teaching and learning process?	3.00	0.750	High
	Aggregate	2.54	0.635	moderate

Table 5 presents a mean and standard deviation analysis to assess the integration of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) facilities into the teaching and learning process in public senior secondary schools within Sapele Local Government Area. The results indicate a predominantly low level of integration, with a moderate aggregate score.

Teachers' incorporation of ICT in teaching is limited, with a low mean score of 1.78 (SD = 0.445). Students report insufficient training in ICT tools (mean = 2.46, SD = 0.615) and low effectiveness of ICT in improving subject understanding (mean = 2.33, SD = 0.583). However, teachers' ICT skills are rated moderately (mean = 3.00, SD = 0.750). An aggregate mean of 2.54 (SD = 0.635) suggests moderate ICT integration, with room for improvement through enhanced training and support for teachers and students.

Research question 4: What challenges and barriers exist that hinder the effective utilization of ICT facilities in education in Sapele Local Government Area?

Table 6 Mean and Standard deviation to determine the existing challenges and barriers exist that hinder the effective utilization of ICT facilities in education within Sapele LGA

S/No1	Statement (n=150; critical Mean = 2.50)	Mean	St.D	Remark
15	The availability of consistent and reliable power supply in our school is inadequate for seamless use of ICT facilities.	3.05	0.762	Low
16	The school lacks sufficient funds allocated for the regular maintenance and upgrading of ICT infrastructure.	2.78	0.695	Low
17	Teachers in our school do not receive regular and effective training on how to integrate ICT tools into their teaching methods.	2.93	0.733	Low
18	The current curriculum in our school does not effectively integrate ICT into various subjects.	2.81	0.703	Low
19	Our school lacks a well-established system for providing technical support to address issues related to ICT hardware and software.	2.91	0.726	Low
	Aggregate	2.90	0.724	Low

Table 6 presents a mean and standard deviation analysis to identify challenges and barriers hindering the effective utilization of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) facilities in education within Sapele Local Government Area. The results reveal that various obstacles contribute to a low level of effective utilization.

Respondents report a mean score (3.05±0.762) for inadequate reliable power, highlighting its impact on ICT use. Additionally, a mean score (2.78±0.695) indicates insufficient funds for ICT maintenance and upgrades, reflecting financial constraints.

Teachers' training on integrating ICT tools into their teaching methods is perceived to be lacking, with a mean score (2.93±0.733). The current curriculum's ineffective integration of ICT into various subjects receives a mean score (2.81±0.703), suggesting a need for curriculum reforms to better incorporate technology.

Furthermore, the mean score (2.91±0.726) for the lack of a well-established system for providing technical support underscores the challenges in addressing issues related to ICT hardware and software.

The aggregate mean score (2.90±0.724) indicates a low overall level of challenges and barriers hindering the effective utilization of ICT facilities in education within Sapele Local Government Area. These findings underscore the importance of addressing issues such as power supply, funding, teacher training, curriculum integration, and technical support to improve the effective use of ICT in education in the region.

Research question 5: How does the utilization of ICT impact on the academic performance of senior secondary school students in Sapele Local Government Area?

Table 7 Summary of PPMC analysis to establish the utilization of ICT impact on the academic performance of senior secondary school students in Sapele Local Government Area

		utilization of ICT	academic performance
Pearson Correlation	utilization of ICT	1.000	.854
	academic performance	.854	1.000

The Pearson correlation in Table 7 shows a strong positive relationship ($r = 0.854$) between ICT utilization and academic performance among senior secondary students in Sapele. This significant correlation indicates that active ICT use enhances academic outcomes, highlighting the need to promote ICT integration for improved performance.

Test of Hypothesis

H₁: The utilization of ICT in Public senior secondary schools in Sapele Local Government Area has significant impact on the teaching and learning, leading to improved academic performance among student

Table 8 Summary of regression analysis to establish if utilization of ICT in Public senior secondary schools in Sapele Local Government has significant impact on the teaching and learning, leading to improved academic performance among student

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	F	B	T	P.val
1	.857b	.734	.731	.422	249.492	0.862	21.460	0.00

Table 8 presents a regression analysis on ICT utilization in Sapele's public senior secondary schools and its impact on teaching, learning, and academic performance. A strong correlation ($R = 0.857$) and R^2 of 0.734 show ICT explains 73.4% of performance variability. The adjusted R^2 is 0.731, with a standard error

of 0.422. A significant F-statistic (249.492) confirms the model's fit, while the beta coefficient (0.862) highlights ICT's strong positive impact.

Findings

This study investigated the state of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in public senior secondary schools in Sapele Local Government Area, Delta State, Nigeria. Below are the summary from the findings.

1. Table 1 shows most respondents were under 25 (71.26%) and female (61.42%), reflecting a young student population.
2. ICT facilities were scarce (Research Question 1), with a low mean score of 1.84 (Table 3), requiring major improvements.
3. ICT integration (Research Question 3) was moderate, with a mean score of 2.54 (Table 5), indicating room for growth.
4. ICT challenges (Research Question 4) were significant (mean score: 2.90, Table 6), including power, funding, training, curriculum, and support issues.

Conclusion

The study on ICT in public senior secondary schools in Sapele, Delta State, Nigeria, reveals a young, predominantly female student population. It highlights the need for improved ICT infrastructure, limited access to resources, and moderate ICT integration in teaching. Challenges such as power supply, funding, teacher training, curriculum integration, and technical support hinder ICT utilization. The study emphasizes the positive impact of ICT on academic performance and the need for greater investment and equitable distribution of ICT resources.

Recommendation

- 1 The Delta State Government should fund ICT infrastructure and support teacher training in public senior secondary schools in Sapele
- 2 Policy makers should establish ICT guidelines and conduct regular assessments to improve ICT integration.

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